

8 Theory Refutes Universal Collapse

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the framework, a Lorentz manifold inside an EL equation it is possible to derive an insight regarding the probability of universal collapse. In particular, such a case would be to shift the terms in the main equation so the invariant acceleration is now directed inward. The phenomena of collapse can be analyzed as well via the coupling constant third representation, i.e. the arrow of time.

Introduction

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad - \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} = 0$$

This equation describes dark energy or time invariant acceleration from areas of extremum curvature on the Lorentz manifold. We assume no data is available from the first three terms, which describe a varying matrix in spatial dimensions. To ensure universe collapse, we need to revert the signs so we will get:

$$\begin{aligned} + \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} &\rightarrow - \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \\ - \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} &\rightarrow + \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} \end{aligned}$$

In other words, the acceleration is now directed inwards, and the new equation is:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial \partial g'}{\partial \partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

Therefore, we have an inward acceleration and areas of negative curving on the Manifold, which agrees with the description of a compressed Lorentz manifold. However, is it reasonable physically to make such a transformation from (1) to (2)? Suppose it is reasonable to change the direction of the acceleration. By looking at the second term:

$$+ \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \rightarrow - \frac{\partial g}{\partial t}$$

Meaning, all the galaxies, clusters of galaxies, which represent extremum curvature on the manifold, must be eliminated and revert their direction inward, toward the manifold. Such shift will be along an inward acceleration and a process of manifold compression. The Process than is synonymous to going from a lower energy state, colder state, to a much Higher state of energy. It is a higher state of energy as it is a process of immense masses compressing inward, Toward a converging Lorenz manifold, such process will be encompassed by friction, heat And high entropy. It is not Lagrangian oriented and not likeable scenario in our framework. There is no need for calculation of hydrogen atoms per unit space when we have the Mathematical equation.

We can also analyze the subject of expansion or collapse by using the coupling constant Equation in its third representation, the arrow of time.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{2}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{3}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \tag{3.1}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1)$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ...$$

$$(1): (30): (128): (850): (9254) ...$$

$$1 > \frac{1}{30} > \frac{1}{128} > \frac{1}{850} \dots$$

$$\xrightarrow{1 > \frac{1}{30} > \frac{1}{128} > \frac{1}{850} \dots}$$

A universal collapse would be to revert the side of the arrow. From weaker and weaker interactions at mega scales, to go for smaller interactions much stronger:

$$\xleftarrow{1 > \frac{1}{30} > \frac{1}{128} > \frac{1}{850} \dots}$$

The physical meaning would be than, stars, galaxies and clusters of galaxies to deform and in an endless succession until we reach quarks and gluons. Such process would require immense amount of energy and it has to happen across all the spectra of the foreseeable universe. In our framework, it means less manifold net variations (positive curving) over time. Physically it does not make sense, it's not Lagrangian oriented. To go from low State of energy and aspire the highest level.

There is no indication that such process could accrue in nature, without artificial Intervene. As far as one knows, it comes to an agreement with the laws of Thermodynamics. Nevertheless, more importantly, in our framework, there is no reason for such unnatural thing to happen.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)